

Conversational Implicature in Austen's *Pride and Prejudice*: A Pragmatic Analysis of the Bennets' Discourse

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ABSTRACT: Studying the implications of literary language is an interesting field of study as its focal analyses are the sophisticated linguistic features used consciously or unconsciously by the authors. Concerning the focus of this paper, the talent of Jane Austen is evident in the domain of literary linguistics. Reviewing the previous literature proves excessive scrutiny of the chief young couples, namely Elizabeth and Darcy. Given that, the present article sheds light on the conversations between the old couple in *Pride and Prejudice*; Mr. and Mrs. Bennet from a pragmatic perspective. The analysis focuses on the very first conversation between the couple as being representative of their relationship. This analysis employs two major pragmatic concepts: the various types of Austin's speech acts as defined by Cutting (2002) and Grice's maxims (1975). Of the thirty-one utterances analyzed in the targeted conversation, 20 are by Mrs. Bennet and 11 by Mr. Bennet. Mrs. Bennet's most frequent speech act is the representative whereas that of Mr. Bennet is the directive. Both violate the maxims, but Mrs. Bennet violates that of quantity as being talkative, unlike Mr. Bennet who violates quality and relation maxims. These analyses demonstrate the misunderstanding and deep psychological gap between Mr. and Mrs. Bennet inferred through their linguistic exchange.

KEYWORD: Conversational implicature, Grice's maxims, Jane Austen, Mr. and Mrs. Bennet, *Pride and Prejudice*, speech act theory

I. INTRODUCTION

A. General Observations

Pragmatics is a branch of linguistics that operates on the assumption that there are interesting things to discover in the details of the language. It is also the study of the relationship between words and the uses of words [1]. This field investigates the interpretations of the words attempting to understand what people mean by their utterances delving deep in the inferences that listeners and readers make, or that -when speaking or writing- they invite others to make. From a philosophical point of view, it is dealing with causes, reasons, and effects rather than with details and circumstances. It goes together with context and depends on it. Literary criticism benefits from the profundity and variety of linguistic analyses. Sell (1995) defines literary pragmatics as the field that examines the pragmatics of literary writing, and reading in which context-realization is of significant importance [2]. Scholars who focus on studying literature via the pragmatics lens exploit the mechanics of language and literature in their linguistic and socio-cultural contexts. Studying the implications of literary language is an interesting field of study as its focal analyses are the sophisticated linguistic features used consciously or unconsciously by the authors.

B. Austen's *Pride and Prejudice*

Jane Austen is an English novelist famous for her six novels, including *Sense and Sensibility* (1811), *Pride and Prejudice* (1813), *Mansfield Park* (1814), *Emma* (1815), *Northanger Abbey* (1817), and *Persuasion* (1817). Generally, these novels reflect the British society at the end of the eighteenth century. Austen's plots often explore women's dependence on marriage searching for prestigious social rank and economic security [3].

Among all the greatest novelists, Jane Austen is "the most difficult to catch her greatness in the twinkling of an eye" [4]. Austen's portrayal of characters is professional, especially considering her character's dialogues that imply sharpness, wit, profundity, and romance. These characters' words and actions show a vivid image of each personality and each event to involve the reader in the novel. Her style is unique, yet recognizable. She exposes people to a new way of life.

Pride and Prejudice is chiefly about Elizabeth Bennet and her pursuit for true love. Elizabeth and her lover, Darcy, are the two chief characters in this novel. The two words, pride and prejudice, highlight the two sides, positive and negative, of any

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personality. With pride, in its positive sense, comes self-esteem, worth, and great accomplishment of oneself. With prejudice, that almost leads to misunderstanding, and intolerance [5].

Jane Austen highlights the relationships between five couples in this novel: the Bennets, Elizabeth and Darcy, Jane and Bingley, Charlotte and Collins, and Lydia and Wickham. Perhaps the most famous opening of any nineteenth-century novel is the opening lines to Jane Austen's *Pride and Prejudice*: "It is a truth universally acknowledged, that a single man in possession of a good fortune, must be in want of a wife" [6]. This sets the marriage motif of the novel. It turns out that rather than the usual case that man needing a wife, the woman is searching for a husband. In *Pride and Prejudice*, four marriages are made which are Elizabeth and Darcy, Jane and Bingley, Charlotte and Collins and Lydia and Wickham, along with the other long-standing marriages between Mr. and Mrs. Bennet and Mr. and Mrs. Gardiners. This study focuses on the old couple Mr. and Mrs. Bennet. They have five daughters (Jane, Elizabeth, Mary, Catherine, and Lydia). Their relationship is initially based on physical attraction. In fact, they differ from each other in the essential perspective of life. Mr. Bennet is an intricate character, though irresponsible and careless for his family. Mr. Bennet's character is one of the basic means through which Austen shows her mastering skills of ironic wit. At the beginning of the novel, he seems interesting when he tries to tease his wife. On the other hand, Mrs. Bennet is too stupid to realize it. Austen describes her as a woman of mean understanding, little information, and uncertain temper [7]. Her life goal is to secure her daughters' marital status. Mr. and Mrs. Bennet are not a well-matched couple. Her silliness does not mix well with his sarcastic wit [7].

II. RELEVANT SCHOLARSHIP

Exploring the previous endeavor in the field reveals some attempts in analyzing Austen's *Pride and Prejudice* and other literary works from a pragmatic perspective. Anggraini et al.'s (2019) study reveals that implicature is excessively employed in the novel by all social classes for purposes such as politeness, live conversation, and sarcasm [8]. Z Y Chang (2010) thoroughly analyzes the novel considering Cooperative Principles (CP) and Politeness Principles (PP) to find out that there is a tendency to indirectly apply the strategy of Face-threatening-act (FTA) to maintain PP at the expense of CP [9]. Like Abi Pandu Wibawa (2017) [10], Fajrina (2014) focuses on examining the maxims employed in Elizabeth Bennet's conversations to find out that Elizabeth's maxim flouting is to either reflect a deeper implication, show wit, or throw a sense of humor [11]. While [4] and [12] generally emphasize the significance of pragmatic analysis of literary works, Du (2016) applies the conversational implicature to Lawrence's *Sons and Lovers* linguistically emphasizing the intimate and influential relationship between Paul and his mother [13]. Consequently, as reviewed, the literature about Austen's novel has not yet pragmatically and exclusively targeted the conversations of Mr. and Mrs. Bennet. The present article is an attempt to fill this gap in the literature.

Therefore, this article aims at investigating the relationship between Mr. And Mrs. Bennet in light of speech act theory and Grice's maxims. Given that, Austen's *Pride and Prejudice* basic themes are marriage and irony as a style. Mr. And Mrs. Bennet are proper characters as an example of the novel in which Austen exposes their relationship and the gap between them. This study is limited to the conversations of Mr. and Mrs. Bennet in Jane Austen's ***Pride and Prejudice***. However, not all the conversations in the novel are included in this study. Only the conversation in chapter one was analyzed because it focuses on the real relationship between the old couple in the novel, and the gap between them.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Based on the theories of Austin (1962), Searle (1969), and Grice (1975) in pragmatics, the theoretical framework of our study is a synthesis of Speech Act Theory and Conversational Implicature [14], [15] and [16].

A. *Speech Act Theory*

Austin (1962) and Searle (1969) are well-known as linguistic philosophers, who are founders of speech act theory. Austin (1962) considers an utterance as an act performed in context by a speaker to a hearer. According to him, performing a speech act consists of performing a locutionary act, the act of producing syntactic utterances, and an illocutionary act, the attempt to accomplish a specific purpose of the speaker. Promising, warning, informing, commanding, and requesting are clear examples of illocutionary acts. The focal concentration in speech act analysis has been on the illocutionary act and the term 'speech act' is usually used interchangeably with the illocutionary act. Cutting and Hidayat has classified five types of speech acts as follows [17] and [18]:

Representatives: Illocutionary acts that represent purposes such as, stating, claiming, hypothesizing, describing, predicting, and telling, insisting, suggesting, or swearing. For example, "she is smart", the speaker can state the sentence based on the fact or just give his or her own opinion.

Expressive: Illocutionary acts that show the speaker's psychological attitude toward an issue such as, congratulating, thanking, deploring, condoling, welcoming, greeting. For example, the saying, "Feel at home!" The utterance is the speaker's expression that they welcomes the addressee.

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Directives: Illocutionary acts to make the addressees do something, such as requesting, commanding, pleading, inviting, questioning, daring, and insisting or suggesting. For example, when someone says, "Turn right" The utterance shows the speaker's request to the hearer to turn right.

Commissive: Illocutionary acts committing the speaker to do something such as promising, threatening, or vowing. When someone says, "I'll take you home", it represents the speaker's promise to do that.

Declarations: Illocutionary acts that create a change in what they refer to, such as, blessing, firing, baptizing, bidding, passing sentence, arresting, or marrying. For example, "I declare you husband and wife."

B. Conversational Implicature

In his *Logic and Conversation* (1975), Grice's theory of conversational implicature is a theory about how to use language in daily communication. Conversational implicature is the relationship between linguistic and utterance meaning which is implied in a person's speech [19]. The cooperative principle is considered as an ideal principle for people to observe, and thus, communicate smoothly. However, people violate cooperative principle in conversations for different purposes and do not always communicate in an explicit, truthful, or relevant way. Therefore, conversational implicature is generated [13].

B.1 Cooperative principles

The study of cooperation in conversation has been the chief focus of Grice (1975). It has been developed in language use and pragmatics considering how individuals communicate cooperatively. According to him, an exchange should involve "cooperative efforts" and have "a common purpose or set of purposes", or at least a mutually accepted direction [20].

Grice proposes four types of maxims: quantity, in which the speakers should be as informative as required, that they should give neither too little information nor too much. In the maxim of quality, the speakers ought to be sincere, i.e., tell the truth. The maxim of relation indicates that the speakers are expected to say a relevant piece of information to the context. In the maxim of manner, the speakers ought to be brief, and avoid ambiguity [17].

Cooper (1998) points out that "they do not role conversation in any sense. We rarely fail to observe the maxims causally, for no reason, but we do fail to observe them intentionally for a variety of reasons" (cited in [20]). One of the reasons is when we say something indirectly so that participants may fail to fulfill the maxims, and this can be achieved through several ways:

A) Violating a maxim, in which the hearer is not aware of breaking the maxims, for example, when a speaker is lying or changing a topic, so that the hearers may be misled as a result [20].

Husband: how much did that new dress cost, darling?

Wife: less than the last one [17]

B) Flouting a maxim, here the hearer is aware of breaking the maxim(s), and, there is an added meaning that the hearer has to infer [20].

X: Well, how do I look?

O: Your shoes are nice [17]

Speech act theory and Grice's Maxims are employed in this paper to analyze the selected conversation between Mr. and Mrs. Bennet. Throughout the several types of Speech acts, we will delve deeper into the hidden meaning intended by the speakers, Mr. Bennet and Mrs. Bennet. Violating maxims is the main focal concept in the analysis of the Conversational implicature between Mr. and Mrs. Bennet. This study is supposed to help to identify which kind of maxims have been broken by the speaker and clarify the reaction of the hearer and how he or she has understood that violation. Also, through the analysis, we will suggest some of the causes that make the speaker break the rules of the maxims.

IV. METHOD

This paper is a qualitative analytic study of text and talk research. It is an attempt to investigate the conversations of Mr. And Mrs. Bennet using Speech act theory (1962) and Grice's maxims (1975). The data of this study has been collected from Jane Austen's novel *Pride and Prejudice* (1813) book. The study population is the conversations between Mr. and Mrs. Bennet in the novel. After the researchers read and gathered the conversations of the old couple which were totally six conversations throughout the novel. The sample selected is the conversation in chapter one purposely. It has been chosen because it represented Mr. and Mrs. Bennet's natural relationship and the gap between them. Also, Austen introduced them at the beginning of her novel that carried the principal theme: marriage and the relationships between the couples before and after marriage. The selected conversation explained the event when Mrs. Bennet heard the news about a handsome rich man who came to the Netherfield. She told her husband about this news and insisted on him to visit this man. The dialogue between them revealed the type of relationship they had from the beginning of the novel.

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To analyze the data, the following steps were followed:

- 1- The researchers read and reread the conversations that were between Mr. and Mrs. Bennet carefully and then they selected one of them.
- 2- The numbers of utterances were identified.
- 3- The researchers applied the theoretical perspectives which were Speech act theory (1962) and Grice's maxims (1975)
- 4- The conversation was analyzed based on the theories.
- 5- In this light, the researchers discussed and analyzed the implied meaning.

To validate the study, we presented a sample of the analysis of one of the conversations between Mr. and Mrs. Bennet (not the one included in the study) (Appendix 1) to three teachers in Hadramout University, of both the English Department of Colleges of Arts and Women; namely, Prof. Hassan Obaid Alfadhly, Assoc. Prof. Khalid Awad Bin Mukhashen, Assoc. Prof. Atef Saleh Altamimi, and Assoc. Prof. Najla'a Abdullah Ateeg. They all agreed upon the structure in general and the analysis in specific. However, one of the teachers suggested putting the analysis on a table to make it clear and easy to comprehend. As he did not explain the manner he suggested or its benefit for the study, the researchers followed the procedures as explained above and as validated by the majority of the referees.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Here, the analysis of the targeted conversation between Mr. and Mrs. Bennet has been conducted from the perspective of Speech act theory and Grice's maxims. This conversation is taken from the first chapter of the novel *Pride and Prejudice*. We took just thirty-one utterances out of fifty-three. In fact, this conversation reflects the real and natural relationship of Mr. and Mrs. Bennet and shows it clearer than the other conversations. Jane Austen starts her novel with this couple because she wanted directly to reflect her message of the marriage that depends only on the physical attraction. Therefore, the researchers select this particular conversation for its significance and details that reveal the gap in their relationship.

A. Data Analysis

"My dear Mr. Bennet" said his lady to him one day, "have you heard that Netherfield Park is let at last. (1).

Mrs. Bennet's utterance (1) is a directive speech act, Mrs. Bennet asks her husband whether he heard about the news of Netherfield Park or not.

Mr. Bennet replied that he had not. (2)

Mr. Bennet's utterance (2) is a representative speech act, Mr. Bennet is saying that he had not heard anything about it. His response is clear, brief and logical. He observed the maxims of quality and manner. However, the speaker (Mrs. Bennet) wants to make her husband curious in order to make him ask for more details, but he did not, which reflects his carelessness.

"But it is" returned she; "for Mrs. Long has just been here, and she told me all about it. (3) —Mr. Bennet made no answer.

Utterance (3) Mrs. Bennet tells her husband about the incident. She tries to give him more information about that place, so it is a representative speech act. However, the silence of Mr. Bennet implies that he is not interested in hearing her, Mr. Bennet did not make any action and he just was silent, in this way he violated the maxim of quality.

"Do you not want to know who has taken it?" (4) cried his wife Impatiently.

In utterance (4) Mrs. Bennet asks her husband again if he wants to know more information about Netherfield. It is a directive speech act because the statement is in the form of question. Mrs. Bennet here is trying to get her husband's attention.

"YOU want to tell me, and I have no objection to hearing it." (5) —This was invitation enough.

Utterance (5) is a commissive speech act, Mr. Bennet expresses his refusal and disinterest in listening to his wife in indirect way. His way of speaking seems that he does not refuse to hear, but in fact, he has no desire to listen to his wife. In one hand Mr. Bennet observed the maxim of relation and quality. On the other hand, he violated the maxim of manner.

"Why, my dear, you must know, (6) Mrs. Long says that Netherfield is taken by a young man of large fortune from the north of England; that he came down on Monday in a chaise and four to see the place, and was so much delighted with it, that he agreed with Mr. Morris immediately; that he is to take possession before Michaelmas, and some of his servants are to be in the house by the end of next week" (7)

Utterance (6) and (7) are representative speech acts. Mrs. Bennet insists to tell her husband the information about the news, despite his refusal. Although Mr. Bennet did not give her any consideration, she details everything. Here, Mrs. Bennet violated the maxims of relation and quantity because she began to detail more than it is required. Also, she tells the truth so she observed the maxim of quality.

What is his name? (8)

Utterance (8) is a directive speech act. From the very beginning, Mrs. Bennet wanted to get the intention of her husband, and now she succeeded in achieving it, and made him ask for the name of the rich man who came to Netherfield

"Bingley". (9)

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Utterance (9) is a representative speech act, here Mrs. Bennet responded to his question, she was clear, brief, and she gave him the name directly. Here, she strictly observed all the maxims.

Is he married or single? (10)

Utterance (10) by Mr. Bennet, is a directive speech act, with the purpose of knowing Mr. Bingley's personal status. Here, Mr. Bennet tries to interact with his wife.

"Oh! Single, my dear, to be sure! (11) A single man of large fortune; four or five thousand a year. (12) What a fine thing for our girls. (13)

Utterance (11), and (12) are representative speech acts, Mrs. Bennet assures that Mr. Bingley is single. Utterance (13) is a directive speech act, she suggests to her husband that Mr. Bingley will be suitable to one of her daughters. She violated the Maxim of quantity by adding extra information in her answer to the question in utterance (10).

"How so? How can it affect them?" (14)

Utterance (14) is a directive speech act, this question implies that he knows and understands what she means but he pretends that he does not understand. Here, Mr. Bennet violated the maxim of quality.

"My dear Mr. Bennet," replied his wife, "how can you be so tiresome! (15) You must know that I am thinking of his marrying one of them."(16)

Utterance (15) is an expressive speech act, which reflects her feelings of being annoyed by the reply of her husband. Utterance (16) is a representative speech act, here, she is expressing her future plan and design to make Mr. Bingley marry one of her daughters.

"Is that his design in settling here?"(17)

Utterance (17) is a directive speech act, here, the question of Mr. Bennet is somehow ironic and shows his careless personality.

"Design! Nonsense, how can you talk so! (18) But it is very likely that he MAY fall in love with one of them, (19) and therefore you must visit him as Soon as he comes (20).

Utterance (18) is an expressive speech act, she is noticing that her husband is not interested in her speech. So, she became nervous. Utterance (19) is a representative speech act, she believes that Mr. Bingley could love one of their daughters. Utterance (20) is a representative speech act, Mrs. Bennet is insisting on her husband to make a visit to Mr. Bingley. In the utterances (18, 19, 20) Mrs. Bennet is talking a lot and breaking the maxim of quantity.

"I see no occasion for that. (21) You and the girls may go, or you may send Them by themselves, which perhaps will be still better, (22) for as you are as Handsome as any of them, Mr. Bingley may like you the best of the Party. (23)

Utterance (21) is a commissive speech act, which shows Mr. Bennet indirect refusal for the request of his wife to visit Mr. Bingley. Utterance (22) is a directive speech act, he is suggesting to his wife that it will be better if she and the girls visit Mr. Bingley instead of him. Utterance (23) is a representative speech act, here is being sarcastic, by claiming that her beauty will steal the spotlight in the party, which implies his mockery of her. He violated the maxim of quality by telling a lie to achieve a specific ironic purpose. At the same time, also he violated the maxim of relation by switching to the subject, which made her forget what she was talking about for a second.

"My dear, you flatter me. (24) I certainly HAVE had my share of beauty, But I do not pretend to be anything extraordinary now. When a woman Has five grown-up daughters, she ought to give over thinking of her own Beauty. (25)."

Utterance (24) is an expressive speech act, Mrs. Bennet understood the literal meaning of her husband speech which is praising her, while in fact he is being sarcastic. Utterance (25) is a representative speech act, she is explaining that her days of being a young beautiful woman is over and now she is caring of her daughters more than herself. Here she observed all the maxims.

"In such cases, a woman has not often much beauty to think of." (26)

Utterance (26) is a representative speech act. Mr. Bennet stating in direct way the fact that an old woman with five grown up daughters does not have any beauty to care of.

"But, my dear, you must indeed go and see Mr. Bingley when he Comes into the neighbourhood". (27)

Utterance (27) is a representative speech act. Mrs. Bennet repeatedly insisting on her husband to visit Mr. Bingley. Here she violated the maxim of quantity by repeating the same speech.

"It is more than I engage for, I assure you." (28)

Utterance (28) is a representative speech act. Mr. Bennet is assuring to his wife in indirect way that he is not interested in visiting Mr. Bingley.

"But consider your daughters. (29) Only think what an establishment it would be for one of them. Sir William and Lady Lucas are determined to Go, merely on that account, for in general, you know, they visit no new comers. (30) Indeed you must go, for it will be impossible for US to visit him If you do not (31)."

Utterance (29), (30) and (31) are representative speech acts. Mrs. Bennet is telling her husband to think about his daughters, because Lucas family may take the advantage of visiting Mr. Bingley. Also, she is reminding her husband of the necessity of visiting Mr. Bingley because they cannot visit him. She violated the maxim of quantity by adding extra information.

B. Discussion

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From the very beginning, Mrs. Bennet tries to initiate a conversation with her husband about a single rich man who moved to their neighborhood, Mr. Bennet is not interested in the subject, he is a smart. Being educated, he uses his quick wit to avoid his silly wife. Mr. Bennet does not declare that he is not interested in the subject, instead he employs his skills of irony. On the other hand, Mrs. Bennet, a woman of mean understanding as Austen describes her in first chapter of the novel, fails to understand the implied meaning of her husband's speech in many ways. At first, Mr. Bennet ignores his wife and does not give her any consideration, but she keeps trying until she succeeds in getting some of his attention, and it is important to note that, she follows a particular style in order to increase his curiosity and asks for information, but Mr. Bennet turns out to be a careless person. The thing that matters to Mrs. Bennet is to get her daughters married, she does not care whether the bridegroom is a stupid character like Collins or a tricky man like Wickham, the most important thing is that a man proposes to one of the girls. Therefore, from the very beginning of the conversation her plan is to arrange a marriage between Bingley and Jane, that is why she asks Mr. Bennet repeatedly to visit Mr. Bingley and through good words about his girls to make the wedding possible. Finally, the relationship between Mr. and Mrs. Bennet is a relationship of a poorly matched couple and their marriage is most certainly a marriage of unequal minds.

VI. CONCLUSION

Conversation is an essential part in daily communication, it is a relationship between the speaker and the hearer, but sometimes people tend to say something and mean something else, for this reason, our study comes to being. This research aims at investigating the relationship between Mr. And Mrs. Bennet from the perspective of speech act theory and Grice's maxims. Chapter one of Austen's *Pride and Prejudice* contains more than fifty-three utterances but the researchers selected only thirty-one utterances as being the most indicative to the relationship between this couple. 11 utterances are made by Mr. Bennet, and 20 by Mrs. Bennet. The Findings of the analysis show that out of 11, 5 of which, are directive, 4 representative, and 2 commissive speech acts. Moreover, for maxims, he did a lot of violations in both maxims of quality and relation, revealing that he did not talk much, and uses irony to make a mockery of his wife. On the other hand, out of Mr. Bennet's 20 utterances, 16 are representative, and 2 for both directive and expressive. For the maxims, she did a lot of violation in the maxim of quantity, which shows that she is a woman who loves to talk too much and always gives extra information.

From the conversation above, we can notice that this old couple suffer from misunderstanding and they are disconnected spiritually, and their relationship has initially been based on shallow attraction. They seem that they do not have any affection towards each other, they barely talk to one another, and their conversation ends with either teasing her or making fun of her in indirect way. Mr. Bennet mainly laughs at the stupidity of his wife's narrow mind, which makes him feel superior to her because of his level of education, which at the long run, widened the gap between them, and separated them from each other emotionally. Besides, the power of language in revealing the true attitudes and feelings is evident and it plays a crucial role in constructing or destructing any relationship among which the most sacred one which is that between wife and husband.

Finally, we recommend conducting more analytic studies from pragmatic point of view in literary works to facilitate the readers' understanding of literary language, and contribute to the enlightenment and appreciation of creative approaches like discourse analysis used in literary works.

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APPENDIX 1: THE REFEREES' SAMPLE

Dear teachers,

We are the students of Hadramout University, College of Arts, English Department Level four. We are conducting our graduate project under the title "Conversational Implicature in Jane Austen's *Pride and Prejudice*: Mr. and Mrs. Bennet as an Example". The aim of this study is to analyze the conversations between Mr. and Mrs. Bennet from the perspective of speech act theory and Grice's maxims. In speech act theory, we focus on the five types of speech acts as explained by Juan Cutting (2002): representative, directive, commissive, expressive, and declarative. As for Grice's maxims, the focus is on the four maxims: quantity, quality, relevance, and manner and whether they are observed, floated or violated. The significance of the study is to give contributions in pragmatics study especially conversational implicature used in literary work.

This is a sample of our analysis. We hope that you check the procedures we are going to follow in analysing the selected conversations.

The Sample

The conversation is taken from Chapter 20 in Jane Austen's *Pride and Prejudice* between Mr. and Mrs. Bennet. It discusses the events when Mr. Collins proposes to Elizabeth. And Mrs. Bennet is struggling to make Elizabeth accept, even she goes so far and threatens her daughter. However, she orders her husband to force Elizabeth to accept the proposal of Mr. Collins. Here, the main goal of Mrs. Bennet is clear which is to get her daughter married.

"*Oh! Mr. Bennet. you are wanted immediately; we are all in an uproar. (1)*". *You must come and make Lizzy marry Mr. Collins for she vows she will not have him, and if you do not make haste he will change his mind and not have her (2).*"

Utterance (1) is an expressive speech act. Here Mrs. Bennet's character is very clear, she can't keep her nerves quite so she comes to Mr. Bennet quickly to solve what does she see as a big problem. Utterance (2) is an order from the speaker to the hearer to do something which called directive speech act. Mrs. Bennet's main goal in the life is so clear in this sentence which is getting her daughters married.

"*I have not the pleasure of understanding you,*"(3) *said he, when she had finished her speech. "of what are you talking?" (4)*

Utterance (3) is a commissive speech act. It has surface and implied meaning. The surface meaning is that he understands what his wife means, but the implied meaning is that he is not interested in the subject. Also his silence emphasizes his attitudes toward his wife. He did that in an indirect way. Utterance (4) is directive speech act. In (3) and (4) the speaker has violated the maxims of quality and manner in which he understands what his wife has said but he made himself ignorant and ambiguous.

"*Of Mr Collins and Lizzy.(5). Lizzy declares she will not have Mr Collins, and Mr Collins begins to say that he will not have Lizzy. (6)*"

Mrs. Bennet's utterances (5) and (6) are representative speech acts. She informs her husband and tells him again about Mr. Collins' proposal to Elizabeth because her husband seems as if he did not understand her. Here, She violates the maxim of quantity and observes the maxims of relation and quality.

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“And what am I to do on the occasion?(7) it seems an hopeless business.”(8)

Utterance (7) is a directive and indirect speech act followed immediately by representative one which is utterance (8). This ironic reply reveals to us the real relationship between them and shows Mr. Bennet's real character which is a careless person towards his